

[Click here to view linked References](#)

1 **A metagenomic study of patients with alveolar osteitis after tooth**
2 **extraction. A preliminary case-control study.**

3
4 Aguilar-Durán, Laura¹
5 Figueiredo, Rui²
6 Seminago, Ramón³
7 Roig, Francisco J⁴
8 Llorens, Carlos⁵
9 Valmaseda-Castellón, Eduard⁶

10
11 (1) DDS, Master of Oral Surgery and Implantology. Faculty of Dentistry – University of
12 Barcelona. Spain.

13 (2) DDS, MS, PhD, Master of Oral Surgery and Implantology. Associate professor of Oral
14 Surgery and Professor of the Master's degree program in Oral Surgery and Implantology.
15 Faculty of Dentistry – University of Barcelona. Researcher at the IDIBELL institute. Spain.

16 (3) BSc Biology. Genomics Unit, CCiTUB – University of Barcelona. Spain.

17 (4) PhD. Biotechvana. Associate Bioinformatician of the Aquatic Pathogens with Public
18 Health Impact Research Line at ERI BioTecMed – University of Valencia. Spain.

19 (5) PhD. Biotechvana. Associate Bioinformatician, CCiT – University of Barcelona. Spain.

20 (6) DDS, MS, PhD. Professor of Oral Surgery. Director of the Master's degree program in
21 Oral Surgery and Implantology, Faculty of Dentistry – University of Barcelona.
22 Researcher at the IDIBELL institute. Spain.

23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30 Short title: Microbiota of alveolar osteitis patients.

31
32
33
34 Key Words: Microbiota, molecular sequencing data, dry socket, tooth extraction, bacteria,
35 microbiology.

36
37
38
39 Corresponding author:

40 Dr. Rui Figueiredo,

41 Facultat de Medicina i Ciències de la Salut (Odontologia) - Universitat de Barcelona,

42 Campus de Bellvitge, Pavelló de Govern 2a planta, Despatx 2.9,

43 08907 - L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Spain.

44 Telephone: (+34) 934024274.

45 E-mail: ruifigueiredo@hotmail.com; www.mastercirugiabucal.com

46
47
48
49 Summary word count: 250

50 Total word count (Abstract to Acknowledgments): 2855

51 Total number of tables/figures: 3 tables, 2 figures

52 Number of references: 34
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
66
67
68
69
70
71
72
73
74
75
76

ABSTRACT

Objective: To identify the microbiome in sockets with alveolar osteitis and compare it with a control group using metagenomic techniques.

Materials and methods: A case-control study was conducted in subjects that had undergone a tooth extraction. Microbiological samples were taken from the sockets of 10 patients with dry socket after tooth extraction (AO group) and 10 patients in whom exodontia resulted in no postoperative complications (Control group). Bacterial DNA was isolated and the 16S rRNA gene was amplified and sequenced. Multiplexed tag-encoded sequencing of DNA from the samples was performed and the reads were processed by Metagenomic Rapid Annotation.

Results: A total of 151 different species were found: 55 bacteria were only found in the AO group, 51 were specific to the control group and 45 were common to both groups. The most frequently found genera in both groups was *Prevotella*. *Prevotella nanceiensis*, *Actinomyces odontolyticus*, *Treponema maltophilum*, *Veillonella dispar*, *Tannerella forsythia* and *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* were found in several patients with alveolar osteitis, with an abundance greater than 0.5%, and were absent in all the control group samples.

Conclusions: Patients who develop alveolar osteitis after dental extractions might have a different microbiota from that of patients without postoperative complications. Since this is a preliminary report, further research is needed to assess whether bacteria play an important role in the etiology of dry socket.

Clinical Relevance: This study seems to indicate that bacteria may play an important role in the alveolar osteitis etiology. Thus, new prevention and treatment strategies should be considered.

77 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

78 The authors would like to thank Mary Georgina Hardinge for English language editing of
79 the manuscript and to Dr. Carlos Noguera for help with collecting the samples.

80

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

81

82 INTRODUCTION

83 Dry socket or alveolar osteitis is a common complication of dental extractions, with an
84 estimated prevalence of around 0.5-5.0% [1]. However, some authors have found higher
85 incidences after the surgical extraction of lower third molars [2-3]. This entity is
86 characterized by an acute, severe pain, with no associated signs of infection or
87 inflammation, starting 2 to 4 days after tooth extraction [2]. Several risk factors have been
88 related to a higher incidence of this complication, including smoking, mandibular teeth,
89 female gender, the use of oral contraceptives, and inadequate intraoperative irrigation,
90 among others [1,2,4].

91 Although this postoperative complication has been extensively addressed in the
92 literature, the etiology remains unclear. Most authors support the view that alveolar
93 osteitis is associated with a fibrinolytic process that leaves the bony walls of the socket
94 exposed to the oral cavity. This fibrinolytic activity has been linked to bacteria involved in
95 periodontal diseases, such as *Treponema denticola* [5,6], and in pericoronitis, such as
96 *Streptococcus spp.*, *Prevotella*, *Bacteroides* and *Peptostreptococcus* [7,8]. Peñarrocha et
97 al.[9] found a significant increase in postoperative pain and alveolar osteitis after dental
98 extractions in patients with poor oral hygiene and previous plaque accumulation. Several
99 studies have also shown that both topical and systemic applications of antibiotics and
100 antiseptics can significantly reduce the occurrence of this complication [2,3,10-13]. These
101 findings suggest that microorganisms may play an active role in the occurrence of
102 alveolar osteitis.

103 To date, more than 700 bacterial taxa have been detected in the oral cavity, many of
104 which cannot be isolated by common culture methods [14]. Several methods have been
105 used to analyse the composition of the oral microbiome, including microscopy, cultural
106 analysis, enzymatic assays and immunoassays [15], but a substantial number of

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

107 microorganisms may be overlooked. Recent techniques, such as pyrosequencing,
108 analyze the microbiome according to the community profile of the 16S ribosomal RNA
109 gene (16S rRNA). It can be extracted from heterogeneous samples, amplified and
110 sequenced [16]. This method can detect most species and identify bacteria that cannot
111 be cultivated with standard techniques.

112 The hypothesis of the present study was that different microbiota are found in
113 postextraction sockets with and without alveolar osteitis. Therefore, the aim of this study
114 was to compare the microbiome in sockets with and without alveolar osteitis, using
115 metagenomic techniques.

116

117 **METHODS**

118 **Subject recruitment**

119 A preliminary case-control study was conducted in subjects who underwent tooth
120 extraction through the Oral Surgery and Implantology Master's degree program of the
121 University of Barcelona. A total sample size of 20 patients was considered sufficient to
122 assess if it would be feasible to perform a larger study. The patients were divided into 2
123 groups. The Alveolar Osteitis group (AO) comprised tooth extraction patients that
124 presented moderate to severe postoperative pain (score of >40) measured on a 100-mm
125 Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) with onset at least 48 hours after the surgical procedure.
126 These cases had an empty socket and presented no apparent signs of infection (no
127 suppuration). The Control Group (CG) was composed of patients that had undergone
128 tooth removal with no postoperative complications (ratio 1:1). The time between tooth
129 extraction and sample collection was similar in both groups since this variable was used
130 as a criterion for matching cases to controls. The STROBE guidelines have been
131 followed in reporting this study.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

132 All the individuals included met the following criteria: (1) age between 18 and 90 years,
133 (2) American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) health status score [17] not higher than
134 3, (3) patients who underwent tooth extractions. The protocol was approved by the
135 institutional review board (Comitè Ètic d'Investigació Clínica, Hospital Odontològic de la
136 Universitat de Barcelona; Protocol number 02/15) of the University of Barcelona Dental
137 Hospital and complied with the Helsinki declaration guidelines for clinical research. All the
138 patients gave signed informed consent to participate in the study.

139 Patients were excluded in the following situations: presence of purulent drainage or
140 inflammation in the socket or use of an antibiotic or antiseptic mouthrinse (bisbiguanides,
141 quarternary ammonium salts and essential oils) shortly before sample collection.

142

143 **Data sampling**

144 A single researcher (LAD) recruited the patients and examined all the clinical records.
145 The data retrieved were age, gender, patient health status based on the ASA Physical
146 Status Classification System [17], current medication, smoking habit (number of
147 cigarettes/day), periodontal disease, history of infection or pericoronitis, surgical variables
148 (date of extraction, local anesthetic, flap design, bone removal, tooth sectioning, suture
149 and surgeon's experience), antibiotic and antiseptic administration and intraoperative
150 complications.

151

152 **Sample collection and DNA Isolation**

153 The samples were collected by placing 3 sterile paper points inside the socket for 10
154 seconds. The samples were then placed in sterile snap-cap tubes and refrigerated
155 at -40°C until they were shipped for analysis.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

156 In the laboratory, the samples were stored in a 1.5-mL microcentrifuge tube and frozen
157 at -80°C until further analysis. To release the bacteria, a phosphate-buffered saline (PBS)
158 was used and the samples were vortexed for 5 minutes. The total DNA was purified with
159 the QiAmp DNA minikit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's
160 protocol for buccal swabs. The amount of DNA extracted was calculated using a Qubit
161 system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA USA).

162

163 **PCR Amplification, Pyrosequencing and Bioinformatic Analyses**

164 Variable regions V1 to V5 of the 16S rRNA genes were amplified using Fast Start High
165 Fidelity PCR Systems (Roche, Mannheim, Germany) and sequenced with the GS Junior
166 Titanium Sequencing kit (Roche, Mannheim, Germany).

167 Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) reactions for V1-V3 and V5-V3 primers were set up
168 with annealing temperatures of 56°C and 50°C respectively. The PCRs were replicated
169 and pooled for each sample. The amplicon library was cleaned with Agencourt AmPure
170 Beads (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions,
171 the concentration of amplicon was estimated using the Qubit dsDNA HS assay kit
172 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA USA), and the size of the amplicon was
173 analyzed using the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer with the Agilent DNA 7500 Kit (Agilent,
174 Santa Clara, California, USA).

175 Multiplexed tag-encoded sequencing of DNA from the samples was performed on the GS
176 Junior platform (Roche Applied Science, Indianapolis, IN, USA).

177 The primers used to amplify the 16SrRNA genes and to introduce Multiplex Identifiers
178 (MIDs) to identify amplicons or samples are available on the NIH Human Microbiome
179 Project website [18]. The resulting fast files were pre-processed with the Prinseq tool [19]

180 by size (over 50bp), quality (minimum quality 30), and N content (rejecting reads with
181 over 5% of Ns and removing terminal Ns).

182

183 **Taxonomic assignment**

184 The processed reads of the 20 samples were uploaded to MG-RAST (Metagenomic
185 Rapid Annotation using Subsystems Technology) [20] server annotations based on
186 hierarchical classification with RDP (Ribosomal Database Project Release 11). The
187 number of uploaded sequences ranged from 10842 to 17475 for AO and from 16740 to
188 36112 for CG, with a mean size of 200nt and 341nt respectively. MG-RAST default
189 clustering parameters within the BLAT algorithm were used. Each read was
190 taxonomically assigned down to the genus and species level with an 80% confidence
191 threshold. Reads giving no bacterial hits were excluded. Artificial replicate sequences
192 produced by sequencing artifacts were removed [21].

193 To estimate bacterial diversity, the number of operational taxonomic units (OTUs) in the
194 samples was determined and a rarefaction analysis was performed. Rarefaction curves
195 were obtained by plotting the number of observed OTUs against the number of
196 sequences, using the MG-RAST platform [20] and the RDP database [22].

197 The total diversity was estimated, clustering sequences at 98% nucleotide identity over a
198 90% sequence alignment length, and rarefaction curves were obtained using the Gpro
199 StaTool package [23] (Fig1a).

200 Venn analysis (Fig1b) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and heatmaps were
201 generated using the GPRO StaTool [23]. The Venn analysis was run on the taxonomic
202 diversity data. The PCA analysis was run on the taxonomic diversity and abundance of
203 each individual sample and on the average of each group (AO and CG) (Fig1c).

204

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

205 **RESULTS**

206 **Demographic, clinical and surgical characteristics of the subjects**

207 Twenty patients were included in the study. Ten belonged to AO and ten to CG. The
208 groups were similar with regard to age, gender and smoking habits (Table 1). No
209 statistically significant differences were found in any of the other variables presented in
210 Table 1, although patients with previous pericoronitis were more common in the AO
211 group.

214 **Microbial sequencing results**

215 The quality of the reads from the sequencing process was evaluated by FastQC
216 pipelines. All the samples presented an excellent average quality (PHRED values over
217 28). The non-assigned reads (non 16SrRNA or sequence artifacts) varied between
218 samples, ranging from 1.68% to 16.38%. The samples used in this study were
219 deposited in the SRA database of GenBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>) under
220 accession numbers SAMN09288233-SAMN09288252.

222 **Oral microbial community**

223 The rarefaction curves for sample size and total taxa identified show that all the
224 taxonomic richness was accounted for in these metagenomes.

225 The taxonomic results showed 151 different species: 55 species were only found in the
226 AO, 51 bacteria were specific to the CG and 44 were common to both groups (Fig1b, 1d,
227 1e and Tables 2 and 3).

229 The genus *Prevotella* was the most commonly identified in all the individuals studied.

230 Alveolar osteitis sites were colonized mainly by *Prevotella* (22%), *Fusobacterium* (7,6%),
231 and *Porphyromonas* (5,8%), whereas the main bacterial groups in the control group were
232 *Prevotella* (18%), *Capnocytophaga* (8%), *Streptococcus* (6%) and *Porphyromonas* (5%).

233 All the bacterial species found can be observed in Tables 2 and 3.

234

235 The following bacterial species were identified exclusively in alveolar osteitis patient
236 samples (AO group) and had a relative abundance of $\geq 0.5\%$: *P. nanceiensis* (2 out of 10
237 AO samples), *A. odontolyticus* (2 out of 10 AO samples), *T. maltophilum* (2 out of 10 AO
238 samples), *V. dispar* (4 out of 10 AO samples), *T. forsythia* (2 out of 10 AO samples) and
239 *L. mesenteroides* (3 out of 10 AO samples).

240

241 Although found in both groups (Table 3), the following pathogens were overrepresented
242 in the AO group: *Prevotella intermedia* (2% AO vs 0.04% CG), *Prevotella melaninogenica*
243 (4% AO vs 0.09% CG), *Parviromas micra* (3% AO vs 0.4% CG) and *Fusobacterium*
244 *nucleatum* (4% AO vs 0.5% CG). Also, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *T. forsythia* and a
245 newly proposed periodontal pathogen, *T. maltophilum*, were only found in the AO group.
246 Pathogens involved in pericoronitis, such as *Streptococcus* spp. and *Peptostreptococcus*
247 *anaerobius*, were found in both groups but were more numerous in the AO group (0.8%
248 vs 0.09% and 0.3% vs <0.09% respectively).

249

250 Of the 151 bacteria identified, 68 were not found in the Human Oral Microbiome
251 Database [14] or the CORE Microbiome [24]. Most of these 68 belonged to the AO
252 group.

253

254 **DISCUSSION**

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

255 The present study has shown the wide range and differing composition of the microbiota
256 present in sockets with and without alveolar osteitis. A total of 151 different species were
257 identified but only 45 were common to both groups. These findings might indicate that
258 bacteria play an important role in the etiology of dry socket.

259 One of the main limitations of this study is the small sample size, which may jeopardize
260 generalization of the outcomes. However, it must be taken into account that no data on
261 studies of this topic using metagenomic techniques have been published. Thus, this
262 paper adds new information to the literature on the microbiota of sockets with and without
263 alveolar osteitis. Furthermore, the outcomes presented indicate that further large sample
264 studies are needed to clarify the etiology of this complication. Next generation
265 sequencing (NGS) of 16S rRNA has made it possible to identify a huge number of
266 bacteria that may remain unnoticed if other common techniques are used. Standard
267 culture media for bacteria were probably the first method that provided valuable data
268 regarding the bacteria present in oral infections [25]. However, this technique is time-
269 consuming and does not identify all the microorganisms present. Molecular methods
270 such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using species specific oligonucleotides and
271 DNA-DNA hybridization have also been widely employed in oral infections, but again do
272 not provide an accurate view of the microbial community. PCR offers great sensitivity and
273 only requires a small amount of DNA of the microbial sample [25], but its ability to
274 discriminate and identify is limited to the oligonucleotides that have been selected, and
275 therefore it neglects an important number of bacteria, especially those that have not been
276 previously linked to the infection studied. NGS has significantly increased the diversity of
277 oral human microbiome identification. Indeed, a recent report published by the authors'
278 department identified 19 species in oral biofilm samples collected from implant abutments

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

279 [26] that were not currently in the Human Oral Microbiome Database (HOMD) [14] or the
280 CORE Microbiome database [24].

281 Alveolar osteitis is a painful complication that occurs frequently after dental extractions.
282 Several reports have linked this disorder to risk factors like smoking [27], gender
283 (women) [27], use of oral contraceptives [27], age [28], difficulty of the extraction [28] and
284 previous history of infection [28]. Regarding prevention, the use of chlorhexidine and
285 systemic antibiotics seems to be effective in reducing the incidence of alveolar osteitis
286 [29-31].

287 Although many papers have been published on this topic, the etiology of dry socket
288 remains unclear. Most authors agree, based on the clinical features of this complication
289 (i.e. presence of an empty socket, pain onset between 48 and 96 hours after surgery and
290 absence of inflammatory signs), that the blood clot either fails to form, or that it is
291 subsequently lysed [6]. However, taking into consideration that antibiotics and antiseptics
292 seem to reduce the incidence of alveolar osteitis and that most of the above-mentioned
293 risk factors (smoking, age, previous history of infection, difficulty of the extraction) are
294 also associated with increased rates of postoperative infections, it may be hypothesized
295 that bacteria play an important role in the etiology of this disorder. Indeed, according to
296 Serrati et al. [32], bacteria or debris might stimulate monocytes/macrophages to release
297 cytokines which can provoke an up-regulation of urokinase-type plasminogen activator
298 (uPA) and plasminogen activator inhibitor 1 (PAI-1) that will lead to clot lysis. The results
299 of the present study seem to support the view that this alteration might have an infectious
300 background, since the microbiota found in the two groups were quite different. Due to the
301 study design (small sample and metagenomic techniques), it is difficult to assess which
302 bacteria are more likely to be linked to alveolar osteitis. However, the following species,
303 which were found with an abundance of >0.5% in 2 or more AO group patients (and were

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

304 absent in the control group), are more likely to be associated with this complication: *P.*
305 *nanceiensis*, *A. odontolyticus*, *T. maltophilum*, *V. dispar*, *T. forsythia* and *L.*
306 *mesenteroides*. *P. intermedia*, *P. melaninogenica*, *P. micra* (3% AO vs 0.4% CG) and *F.*
307 *nucleatum* might also be involved, since they were over-represented in the dry socket
308 samples. *L. mesenteroides* may be an important microorganism in this complication, since
309 it was found in 30% of the AO samples and this species has been used in the
310 pharmaceutical and chemical industries as an anticoagulant to prevent the formation of
311 blood clots [33-34]. Moreover, this bacteria was not present in the CG.
312 These outcomes indicate the need for additional research on the role of bacteria in such
313 a clinically-relevant topic. Thus, future studies should consider using metagenomic
314 techniques in larger samples of patients, which must also include a control group.
315 In conclusion, the microbiota of patients who develop alveolar osteitis after dental
316 extractions might be different from that of patients without postoperative complications.
317 Since this is a preliminary report, further research is needed to assess whether bacteria
318 play an important part in the etiology of dry socket.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

320 **Compliance with Ethical Standards**

321

322 **Conflict of interest:** Dr. Rui Figueiredo reports grants from the Faculty of Dentistry -
323 University of Barcelona during the conduct of the study. He also reports grants, personal
324 fees and non-financial support from Mozo-Grau (Valladolid, Spain), grants from
325 Mundipharma Research (Cambridge, United Kingdom), personal fees from BioHorizons
326 Ibérica (Madrid, Spain), Inibsa Dental (Lliça de Vall, Spain), Dentsply implants Iberia
327 (Barcelona, Spain) and Araguaney Dental (Barcelona, Spain) outside the submitted work.
328 Dr. Eduard Valmaseda-Castellón reports grants from the Faculty of Dentistry - University
329 of Barcelona during the conduct of the study. He also reports grants, personal fees and
330 non-financial support from MozoGrau, personal fees from BioHorizons Ibérica, personal
331 fees from Inibsa Dental, and personal fees from Dentsply implants Iberia outside the
332 submitted work. Dr. Laura Aguilar-Durán, Dr. Ramón Seminago, Dr. Carlos Llorens and
333 Dr. Francisco J. Roig report grants from the Faculty of Dentistry - University of Barcelona
334 to conduct the present study. The authors declare no other conflicts of interest regarding
335 this study. The present research was conducted by the Dental and Maxillofacial
336 Pathology and Therapeutics research group at the IDIBELL Institute and was funded by a
337 postgraduate research grant from the Faculty of Dentistry of the University of Barcelona
338 (4000€).

339

340 **Funding:** The present research was partially funded (4000€) with a postgraduate research
341 grant from the Faculty of Dentistry of the University of Barcelona.

342

343 **Ethical approval:** All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in
344 accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee

1 345 and with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its latter amendments or comparable ethical
2
3 346 standards.
4
5 347
6
7 348 **Informed consent:** Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in
8
9
10 349 the study.
11
12 350
13
14 351
15
16 352
17
18 353
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

354 **REFERENCES**

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

355 1. Vezeau PJ (2000) Dental extraction wound management: medicating
356 postextraction sockets. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 58:531-537

357 2. Blum IR (2002) Contemporary views on dry socket (alveolar osteitis): a clinical
358 appraisal of standardization, aetiopathogenesis and management: a critical
359 review. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 31:309-317

360 3. Noroozi AR, Philbert RF (2009) Modern concepts in understanding and
361 management of the “dry socket” syndrome: comprehensive review of the
362 literature. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 107:30-35

363 4. Alexander RE (2000) Dental extraction wound management: a case against
364 medicating postextraction sockets. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 58:538-551

365 5. Nitzan D, Sperry JF, Wilkins TD (1978) Fibrinolytic activity of oral anaerobic
366 bacteria. *Arch Oral Biol* 23:465-470

367 6. Nitzan DW (1983) On the genesis of “dry socket”. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 41:706-
368 710.

369 7. Brescó-Salinas M, Costa-Riu N, Berini-Aytés L, Gay-Escoda C (2006) Antibiotic
370 susceptibility of the bacteria causing odontogenic infections. *Med Oral Patol Oral*
371 *Cir Bucal* 11:70-75

372 8. Poeschl PW, Spusta L, Russmueller G et al (2010) Antibiotic susceptibility and
373 resistance of the odontogenic microbiological spectrum and its clinical impact on
374 severe deep space head and neck infections. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol*
375 *Oral Radiol Endod* 110:151-156

376 9. Peñarrocha M, Sanchis JM, Sáez U, Gay C, Bagán JV (2001) Oral hygiene and
377 postoperative pain after mandibular third molar surgery. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral*
378 *Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 92:260-264

379 10. Hedström L, Sjögren P (2007) Effect estimates and methodological quality of
380 randomized controlled trials about prevention of alveolar osteitis following tooth
381 extraction: a systematic review. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol*
382 *Endod* 103:8-15

383 11. Laird WR, Stenhouse D, MacFarlane TW (1972) Control of postoperative
384 infection. A comparative evaluation of clindamycin and phenoxymethylpenicillin.
385 *Br Dent J* 133:106-109

- 1 386 12. Larsen PE (1991) The effect of chlorhexidine rinse on the incidence of alveolar
2 387 osteitis following the surgical removal of impacted third molars. *J Oral Maxillofac*
3 388 *Surg* 49:932-937
- 4 389 13. Haraji A, Rakhshan V, Khamverdi N, Alishahi HK (2013) Effects of intra-alveolar
5 390 placement of 0.2% chlorhexidine bioadhesive gel on dry socket incidence and
6 391 postsurgical pain: a double-blind split-mouth randomized controlled clinical trial. *J*
7 392 *Orofac Pain* 27:256-262
- 8 393 14. Human Oral Microbiome Database (HOMD) c2007-2018 Cambridge (MA): The
9 394 Forsyth Institute; [accessed 2016 April]. <http://www.homd.org/>
- 10 395 15. Kilian M, Chapple IL, Hannig M et al (2016) The oral microbiome – an update for
11 396 oral healthcare professionals. *Br Dent J* 221:657-666
- 12 397 16. Zarco MF, Vess TJ, Ginsburg GS (2012) The oral microbiome in health and
13 398 disease and the potential impact on personalized dental medicine. *Oral Dis*
14 399 18:109-120
- 15 400 17. ASA Physical Status Classification System (2014) Washington DC: American
16 401 Society of Anesthesiologists; [updated October 15 2014; accessed April 20 2017]
17 402 <http://www.asahq.org/resources/clinical-information/asa-physical-status->
18 403 [classification-system](http://www.asahq.org/resources/clinical-information/asa-physical-status-)
- 19 404 18. Group JCHMPDGWG. 16S 454 Sequencing Protocol HMP Consortium (2010)
20 405 Available at: http://www.hmpdacc.org/doc/16S_Sequencing_SOP_4.2.2.pdf.
21 406 Assessed January 25, 2016
- 22 407 19. Schmieder R, Edwards R (2011) Quality control and preprocessing of
23 408 metagenomic datasets. *Bioinformatics* 27:863–864
- 24 409 20. Meyer F, Paarmann D, D'Souza M et al (2008) The metagenomics RAST server -
25 410 a public resource for the automatic phylogenetic and functional analysis of
26 411 metagenomes. *BMC Bioinformatics* 9:386-394
- 27 412 21. Gomez-Alvarez V, Teal TK, Schmidt TM (2009) Systematic artifacts in
28 413 metagenomes from complex microbial communities. *ISME J* 3:1314-1317
- 29 414 22. Wang Q, Garrity GM, Tiedje JM, Cole JR (2007) Naive Bayesian classifier for
30 415 rapid assignment of rRNA sequences into the new bacterial taxonomy. *Appl*
31 416 *Environ Microbiol* 73:5261–5267
- 32 417 23. Futami R, Muñoz-Pomer L, Viu JM et al (2011) GPRO The professional tool for
33 418 annotation, management and functional analysis of omic databases. *Biotechnava*
34 419 *Bioinformatics* 2011-SOFT3

1 420 24.OSU CORE database, Oral Microbiome. Available at:
2 421 <http://microbiome.osu.edu/sequences>. Assessed November 21, 2016
3 422 25.Charalampakis G, Belibasakis GN (2015) Microbiome of peri-implant infections:
4 423 lessons from conventional, molecular and metagenomic analyses. *Virulence*
5 424 6:183-187
6
7 425 26. Cortés-Acha B, Figueiredo R, Seminago R, Roig FJ, Llorens C, Valmaseda-
8 426 Castellón E (2017) Microbiota analysis of biofilms on experimental abutments
9 427 mimicking dental implants: an in vivo model. *J Periodontol* 88:1090-1104
10
11 428 27.Bienek DR, Filliben JJ (2016) Risk assessment and sensitivity meta-analysis of
12 429 alveolar osteitis occurrence in oral contraceptive users. *J Am Dent Assoc*
13 430 147:394-404
14
15 431 28.Taberner-Vallverdú M, Sánchez-Garcés MÁ, Gay-Escoda C (2017) Efficacy of
16 432 different methods used for dry socket prevention and risk factor analysis: A
17 433 systematic review. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal* 22:e750-e758
18
19 434 29.Rodríguez Sánchez F, Rodríguez Andrés C, Arteagoitia Calvo I (2017) Does
20 435 chlorhexidine prevent alveolar osteitis after third molar extractions? Systematic
21 436 review and meta-analysis. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 75:901-914
22
23 437 30.Ramos E, Santamaría J, Santamaría G, Barbier L, Arteagoitia I (2016) Do
24 438 systemic antibiotics prevent dry socket and infection after third molar extraction?
25 439 A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral*
26 440 *Radiol* 122:403-425
27
28 441 31.Lodi G, Figini L, Sardella A, Carrassi A, Del Fabbro M, Furness S (2012)
29 442 Antibiotics to prevent complications following tooth extractions. *Cochrane*
30 443 *Database Syst Rev* 11:CD003811
31
32 444 32.Serrati S, Margheri F, Bruschi S et al (2006) Plasminogen activators and inhibitor
33 445 type-1 in alveolar osteitis. *Eur J Oral Sci* 114:500-503
34
35 446 33.Seo ES, Lee JH, Park JY, Kim D, Han HJ, Robyt JF (2005) Enzymatic synthesis
36 447 and anti-coagulant effect of salicin analogs by using the *Leuconostoc*
37 448 *mesenteroides* glucansucrase acceptor reaction. *J Biotechnol* 117:31-38
38
39 449 34.Ates O (2015) Systems biology of microbial exopolysaccharides production.
40 450 *Front Bioeng Biotechnol* 3:200
41
42 451
43
44 452
45
46 453

454

Table 1 Characteristics of the subjects			
Parameters	Alveolar osteitis	Control group	p-value
Patient age	30 (19 - 35)	29 (21 - 40)	
Gender (M/F)	3/7	4/6	0.639
Smoker (Y/N)	1/9	2/8	0.528
Oral contraceptives in women	2	0	
Oral hygiene (H/G/P)	4/5/1	7/3/0	0.257
History of infection or pericoronitis (Y/N)	6/4	2/8	0.063
Surgical extraction (Y/N)	6/4	5/5	0.653
Surgeon's experience (1 st /2 nd /3 rd year resident)	5/3/2	2/4/4	0.341
M: male, F: female, H: healthy, G: gingivitis, P: periodontitis, Y: yes, N: no.			

455

456 Table 1: Main patient variables.

TABLE 2							
Abundance and overrepresentation of identified species in Alveolar Osteitis group only							
Species	Abundance	%	Gram	Species	Abundance	%	Gram
<i>Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans</i>	117	0.09		<i>Halanaerobium saccharolyticum</i> subsp. <i>saccharolyticum</i>	930	0.8	-
<i>Actinomyces odontolyticus</i>	3250	3	+	<i>Halothiobacillus hydrothermalis</i>	1039	0.9	-
<i>Aggregatibacter segnis</i>	84	0.09	-	<i>Lactobacillus catenaformis</i>	4	<0.09	+
<i>Anaplasma phagocytophilum</i>	6	<0.09	-	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i>	30	<0.09	+
<i>Atopobium minutum</i>	347	0.3	+	<i>Leptotrichia hofstadii</i> F0254	385	0.3	-
<i>Bacteroides acidifaciens</i>	313	0.3	-	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	819	0.7	+
<i>Blautia producta</i>	199	0.2	+	<i>Megasphaera micronuciformis</i>	16	<0.09	-
<i>Butyrate-producing bacterium SM4/1</i>	3	<0.09	+	<i>Mitsuokella multacida</i>	6	<0.09	-
<i>Butyrate-producing bacterium SS3/4</i>	328	0.3	+	<i>Mycoplasma salivarium</i>	25	<0.09	+
<i>Butyricimonas synergistica</i>	152	0.2	-	<i>Neisseria pharyngis</i>	342	0.3	-
<i>Candidatus Desulforudis audaxviator</i> MP104C	405	0.3		<i>Nymphaea alba</i>	1030	0.9	
<i>Chryseobacterium</i> sp. KM	563	0.5		<i>Parabacteroides goldsteinii</i>	109	0.09	-
<i>Clostridium aminobutyricum</i>	24	<0.09	+	<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i>	59	0.09	-
<i>Clostridium longisporum</i>	975	0.9	+	<i>Prevotella copri</i>	68	0.09	-
<i>Clostridium</i> sp. MK8	354	0.3	+	<i>Prevotella multiformis</i>	5	<0.09	-
<i>Clostridium ultunense</i>	1679	1	+	<i>Prevotella nanceiensis</i>	1521	1	-
<i>Cytophaga</i> sp. MBIC04667	3	<0.09	-	<i>Prevotella oulorum</i>	284	0.3	-
<i>Dialister pneumosintes</i>	1617	1	-	<i>Prevotella pleuritidis</i>	942	0.8	-
<i>Embryophyte environmental sample</i>	12	<0.09		<i>Prevotella veroralis</i>	836	0.7	-
<i>Eubacterium cellulosolvens</i>	5	<0.09	+	<i>Robinsoniella peoriensis</i>	4723	4	+
<i>Eubacterium hallii</i>	738	0.6	+	<i>Roseburia cecicola</i>	369	0.3	+
<i>Eubacterium rectale</i>	1159	1	+	<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>	171	0.2	+
<i>Eubacterium saburreum</i>	346	0.3	+	<i>Tannerella forsythia</i>	1398	1	-
<i>Flavobacterium columnare</i>	638	0.5	-	<i>Treponema lecithinolyticum</i>	185	0.2	-
<i>Flavobacterium denitrificans</i>	64	0.09	-	<i>Treponema maltophilum</i>	1146	1	-
<i>Fusobacterium</i>	7	<0.09	-	<i>Treponema</i>	79	0.09	-

<i>necrophorum</i>				<i>medium</i>			
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum subsp. animalis</i>	576	0.5	-	<i>uncultured alpha proteobacterium</i>	39	<0.09	
<i>Granulicatella elegans</i>	1182	1	+	<i>unidentified proteobacterium</i>	10	<0.09	
<i>Haemophilus sp. CCUG 15949</i>	69	0.09		<i>Veillonella dispar</i>	3368	3	-
Abundance and overrepresentation of identified species in Control group only							
Species	Abundance	%	Gram	Species	Abundance	%	Gram
<i>Actinomyces israelii</i>	263	0.1	+	<i>Mesoplasma lactucae</i>	932	0.4	+
<i>Actinomyces viscosus</i>	3035	1	+	<i>Moraxella nonliquefaciens</i>	5	<0.09	-
<i>Arthrobacter agilis</i>	9451	4	+	<i>Mycoplasma faucium</i>	31	<0.09	+
<i>Bacteroides barnesiae</i>	1	<0.09	-	<i>Porphyromonas gingivicanis</i>	1320	0.6	-
<i>Blautia sp. Ser8</i>	977	0.4		<i>Prevotella aurantiaca</i>	26	<0.09	-
<i>Bradyrhizobium japonicum</i>	207	0.09	-	<i>Prevotella baroniae</i>	757	0.3	-
<i>Butyrivibrio fibrisolvens</i>	4992	2	-	<i>Prevotella bergensis</i>	8	<0.09	-
<i>Campylobacter gracilis</i>	259	0.1	-	<i>Prevotella bivia</i>	2100	0.9	-
<i>Campylobacter showae</i>	360	0.2	-	<i>Prevotella marshii</i>	1128	0.5	-
<i>Capnocytophaga canimorsus</i>	4497	2	-	<i>Prevotella oralis</i>	161	0.09	-
<i>Clostridium acetobutylicum</i>	10	<0.09	+	<i>Prevotella sp. RS2</i>	1612	0.7	-
<i>Clostridium aminovalericum</i>	3921	2	+	<i>Propionibacterium acidipropionici</i>	223	0.09	+
<i>Clostridium bifermentans</i>	942	0.4	+	<i>Pyramidobacter piscolens</i>	6237	3	-
<i>Clostridium hathewayi</i>	1285	0.6	-	<i>Rhodococcus sp. 28/19</i>	339	0.1	+
<i>Clostridium sphenoides</i>	45	<0.09	+	<i>Riemerella anatipestifer</i>	24	<0.09	-
<i>Corynebacterium kutscheri</i>	1394	0.6	-	<i>Streptococcus anginosus</i>	6604	3	+
<i>Desulfocaldus sp. Hobo</i>	852	0.4		<i>Streptococcus australis</i>	4246	2	+
<i>Elizabethkingia meningoseptica</i>	57	<0.09	-	<i>Streptococcus salivarius</i>	2024	0.9	+
<i>Ewingella americana</i>	491	0.2	-	<i>Synergistetes bacterium SGP1</i>	9	<0.09	-
<i>Fusobacterium canifelinum</i>	74	<0.09	-	<i>Treponema bryantii</i>	1	<0.09	-
<i>Gemella haemolysans</i>	1372	0.6	+	<i>Treponema denticola</i>	4803	2	-
<i>Geodermatophilus obscurus</i>	3	<0.09	+	<i>Treponema vincentii</i>	63	0.04	-
<i>Lachnospiraceae bacterium 14-2</i>	993	0.4	-	<i>Veillonella atypica</i>	123	0.04	-
<i>Leptotrichia wadei</i>	43	<0.09	-	<i>Veillonella parvula</i>	828	0.3	-
<i>Macrococcus carouelicus</i>	2882	1	+				

458 Table 2. Abundance and overrepresentation of identified species identified in only one of
459 the study groups (Alveolar Osteitis (AO) or Control group (CG)).
460

TABLE 3						
Abundance and overrepresentation of identified species common to both groups						
Species	Alveolar osteitis		Control Group		Over-represented	Gram
	Abundance	%	Abundance	%		
<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>	246	0.3	5132	2	Control	+
<i>Abiotrophia para-adiacens</i>	487	0.4	1925	0.8	Control	+
<i>Actinomyces naeslundii</i>	109	0.09	4378	2	Control	+
<i>Atopobium vaginae</i>	534	0.4	7712	3	Control	+
<i>Butyrivibrio hungatei</i>	4759	4	1650	0.7	Dry socket	-
<i>Capnocytophaga gingivalis</i>	509	0.4	9329	4	Control	-
<i>Capnocytophaga ochracea</i>	1717	1	2382	1	-	-
<i>Capnocytophaga sputigena</i>	201	0.2	6040	3	Control	-
<i>Clostridium paradoxum</i>	81	0.09	3703	2	Control	+
<i>Desulfotomaculum thermosapovorans</i>	84	0.09	303	0.1	-	+
<i>Dialister pneumosintes</i>	1617	1	189	0.09	Dry socket	-
<i>Eikenella corrodens</i>	386	0.3	1429	0.6	Control	-
<i>Eubacterium sp. WAL 17363</i>	1273	1	1253	0.6	-	+
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	5109	4	1199	0.5	Dry socket	-
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum subsp. polymorphum</i>	1676	1	3266	1	-	-
<i>Fusobacterium periodonticum</i>	1249	1	1333	0.6	-	-
<i>Gemella morbillorum</i>	300	0.3	390	0.2	-	+
<i>Granulicatella adiacens</i>	559	0.5	1599	0.7	Control	+
<i>Haemophilus haemolyticus</i>	2	<0.09	470	0.2	Control	-
<i>Haemophilus parainfluenzae</i>	1783	2	1327	0.6	-	-
<i>Parvimonas micra</i>	3149	3	922	0.4	Dry socket	+
<i>Peptostreptococcus anaerobius</i>	343	0.3	4	<0.09	Dry socket	+
<i>Porphyromonas catoniae</i>	4982	4	7425	3	-	-
<i>Porphyromonas endodontalis</i>	1500	1	2594	1	-	-
<i>Prevotella buccae</i>	7498	7	13532	6	-	-
<i>Prevotella denticola</i>	1765	2	2480	1	-	-
<i>Prevotella enoeca</i>	45	0.09	23	<0.09	-	-
<i>Prevotella intermedia</i>	1870	2	95	0.04	Dry socket	-
<i>Prevotella loescheii</i>	183	0.2	6599	3	Control	-
<i>Prevotella maculosa</i>	91	0.09	9	<0.09	Dry socket	-
<i>Prevotella melaninogenica</i>	4079	4	169	0.09	Dry socket	-
<i>Prevotella nigrescens</i>	1696	1	689	0.3	Dry socket	-
<i>Prevotella oris</i>	4060	4	4963	2	-	-
<i>Prevotella pallens</i>	277	0.3	4	<0.09	Dry socket	-
<i>Prevotella ruminicola</i>	45	0.09	75	0.04	-	-
<i>Prevotella salivae</i>	186	0.2	5588	2	Control	-
<i>Selenomonas lacticifex</i>	118	0.09	534	0.2	Control	-
<i>Selenomonas ruminantium</i>	736	0.6	940	0.4	-	-

<i>Streptococcus</i>	923	0.8	202	0.09	Dry socket	+
<i>Streptococcus intermedius</i>	922	0.8	24	<0.09	Dry socket	+
<i>Streptococcus mitis</i>	1516	1	827	0.3	Dry socket	+
<i>uncultured bacterium</i>	19265	17	39673	17	Control	
<i>uncultured beta proteobacterium</i>	113	0.09	580	0.3	Control	
<i>uncultured Kingella sp.</i>	750	0.7	4896	2	Control	
<i>unidentified</i>	78	0.09	7914	3	Control	
<i>Veillonella rogosae</i>	1460	1	89	0.04	Dry socket	-

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10 461
11
12 462
13 463
14 464
15 465
16 466
17 467
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Table 3. Abundance and overrepresentation of identified species common to both groups.

468 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

469
470 **Figure 1 A** Rarefaction plot showing a curve of annotated species richness. This curve is
471 a plot of the total number of distinct species annotations as a function of the number of
472 sequences sampled. **B** Venn diagram demonstrating bacterial taxonomic distribution
473 between diseased and healthy samples. **C** Principal Component Analysis (PCA)
474 relationships among the groups of samples. The circles surround the samples belonging
475 to the same group.

476 **Figure 2 A and B** Taxonomic spectrum visualized with Krona chart of metagenome read
477 counts. The circles represent taxonomic classifications in ascending order up to the
478 family level (outermost circle). Less abundant taxa are listed outside the charts together
479 with their relative abundance. Obtained from raw data using the MG-RAST server (A:
480 Alveolar Osteitis samples pool and B: Control Group).

A

